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*Daryna Norik**Науковий керівник: д-р іст. наук, проф. Астахова К. В.***TRANSFORMATION OF THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN
HIGHER EDUCATION AND THE LABOR MARKET:
HISTORICAL NARRATIVES**

This article examines the evolution of relations between higher education institutions and the labor market. The relevance of this topic is determined by the growing demands for higher quality of education and the need to align educational programs with the needs of the modern economy.

The author analyzes the evolution of these relationships from the 18th to the 21st century – from the establishment of the first universities to the modern digital age. The writer demonstrates how the functions of higher education have changed under the influence of social and economic transformations, scientific and technological progress, and globalization processes. Highlights how the functions of higher education have changed, particularly in terms of professional training, innovative activity, and the structure of interaction with employers.

The article relies on extensive academic research covering various historical stages of education and labor market development. It highlights how universities have adapted their educational programs, training formats, and models of interacting with the market in response to the demands of the times – from the classic model of academic autonomy to the modern model of the “knowledge triangle”: education – science – business.

The study’s findings confirm the need for strategic modernization in higher education in order to improve its relevance to the real needs of the economy and society. The work contributes to a deeper understanding of the historical logic of change and outlines prospects for developing interaction between education and the labor market.

Key words: labor market, higher education, historical interaction, adaptation to the labor market, modernization of education, employment.

Норік Дарина Станіславівна. Трансформація стосунків вищої школи та ринку праці: історичні наративи.

У статті розглядається еволюція взаємин між вищими навчальними закладами та ринком праці в історичній перспективі. Актуальність теми

зумовлена зростаючими вимогами до якості підготовки фахівців та необхідністю узгодження освітніх програм із потребами сучасної економіки.

Автором проаналізовано еволюцію цих взаємин від XVIII до XXI ст. – з часів виникнення перших університетів до сучасної цифрової доби. Показано, як змінювались функції вищої освіти під впливом соціально-економічних трансформацій, науково-технічного прогресу та глобалізаційних процесів. Висвітлено, як змінювались функції вищої школи, зокрема в аспекті професійної підготовки, інноваційної діяльності та структурі взаємодії з роботодавцями.

У роботі використано значний масив наукових праць, статей та досліджень, які охоплюють різні історичні етапи розвитку освіти та ринку праці. Висвітлено, як університети адаптували освітні програми, формати підготовки та форми взаємодії з ринком відповідно до запитів часу – від класичної моделі академічної автономії до сучасної моделі «трикутника знань»: освіта – наука – бізнес.

Результати дослідження підтверджують необхідність стратегічної модернізації вищої освіти в контексті підвищення її відповідності реальним потребам економіки та суспільства. Робота сприяє глибшому розумінню історичної логіки змін та окреслює перспективи розвитку взаємодії між освітою та ринком праці.

Ключові слова: ринок праці, вища освіта, історія взаємодії, адаптація до ринку праці, модернізація освіти, працевлаштування.

In modern conditions of rapid socio-economic change, the issue of graduate employment is becoming particularly relevant. One of the key factors influencing this process is the interaction between universities and the job market. Historically, this interaction did not develop immediately: from the elite educational institutions of ancient times, where education was available only to the privileged classes, to medieval universities, which became centers for professional training in the church, law, and medicine.

The relevance of the research is determined by the need for a deeper understanding of how the links between universities, science, and the manufacturing sector were formed in different historical periods. Analysis of this evolution makes it possible to trace how changes in approaches to training specialists capable of responding to the demands of the economic sector have occurred.

The purpose of the study is to analyze how forms of cooperation between

universities and enterprises were formed and changed in different historical periods, particularly in the context of providing graduates with opportunities for their professional development.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks have been identified:

- to analyze the main stages in the development of relations between universities and businesses from the 19th to the early 21st centuries;
- to analyze how the functions of universities have transformed in line with changes in the labor market;
- to identify current trends and challenges in cooperation between higher education institutions and employers regarding graduate employment.

Despite the importance of the topic, the academic community has devoted considerably lower attention to it than to other aspects of educational and labor relations. This has led to significant gaps in the study of these processes, which, unfortunately, hinder a comprehensive understanding of the role universities played in training employees. Although there are some insightful contributions, such as I. Posokhov's "University students in the Russian Empire in the 19th and early 20th centuries and local society" which examines the student community as a distinct social layer in detail [11], or V. Bakirov's work «V. N. Karazin Kharkiv National University: milestones in history» which analyzes the activities of this university's graduates in a historical context [2]. Equally important is the work of V. Kornienko, "Characteristics of the formation of the national university education system" which describes in detail the reasons for the creation of the first higher education institutions [5]. However, despite the existence of these studies, the literature directly addressing the research topic remains limited.

Modern European universities are the result of a long and complex historical process. Their establishment was driven by the emergence of new social groups, growing demand for highly qualified specialists, and the development of trade and industry, which created a need for specialists in these fields. In addition, the desire for a culture of law and social stability also became an important factor in the development of higher education. One of the main conditions for the progress of universities was their autonomy, as the independence of educational institutions contributed to the development of critical thinking and academic freedom. However, no

education system could develop effectively without continuous reforms that ensured its adaptation to changes in society and the economy [9].

The beginning of university education in the Russian Empire is closely linked to the reforms of Peter I. The decree on the “Establishment of the Academy of Sciences and Arts” was an important step in creating the Academic University and Gymnasium. The official opening of these institutions took place on December 27, 1725. This period was characterized by a significant increase in the state’s need for highly qualified specialists, which required the implementation of rapid and large-scale measures for the development of education. At the same time, special attention was paid to borrowing European experience and attracting leading scientists from other countries to form a new educational system [5].

In the mid-18th century, an important educational institution was founded – Moscow University, which opened its doors on January 25, 1755. This university became the first independent higher educational institution in the Russian Empire. From the late 1750s, its graduates were sent to leading European universities for further training for professorial positions. Internships at technical universities in Europe, where educational ideas were actively developing, were of particular importance to them [5].

In the 19th century, with the development of capitalist relations and changes in management and economics, the government was forced to pay more attention to the issue of professional education. The increasing demand for qualified specialists in various sectors of the economy, manufacturing, and public administration required the creation of new educational programs and educational institutions that would meet the requirements of the time [7].

The basis of public education was the introduction the principle of centralized management. Due to socio-economic changes, there was a need to train a large number of qualified workers. To this end, teacher training colleges were established in Ukraine in the mid-19th century to prepare primary school teachers [7].

The high demand for qualified teachers made the employment process easier, providing young professionals with opportunities for career growth. Over a period of five years, from 1808 to 1812, 83 people became teachers, 39 chose civil service, and 18 entered military service [1].

By the end of the 1850s, women in the Russian Empire received secondary education mainly in institutes and diocesan schools, private boarding schools, and church-affiliated schools under the Ministry of Public Education. At the same time, most young women were educated at home by governesses or private tutors, and the quality of education depended on the family's financial situation. The expansion of girls' secondary schools was an important step in the systematization and formalization of secondary education for girls. A symbolic indicator of change was the fact that on the eve of World War I, the number of women with secondary education exceeded the number of men [10].

Engineering and industrial institutes were an important part of the higher education system, bringing together educational facilities with diverse organizational structures and specializations. Among them were two-faculty technological institutes, multi-faculty polytechnic universities, and single-industry engineering schools specializing in such areas as mining, transport, electrical engineering, and architecture. At the end of the 19th century, the most popular were technological institutes, in particular the St. Petersburg, Kharkiv, and Moscow Technical Schools, which trained engineers for the mechanical and chemical industries. Graduates of such institutions received specialized titles, including metallurgical engineer, electrical engineer, mechanical engineer, and other professional titles depending on the faculty [4].

Between 1884 and 1905, students actively wanted to go beyond traditional lecture courses and get involved in scientific work. They worked in clinics and laboratories, researching topical issues, writing essays and various studies [1].

During the period of rapid industrial development in Ukraine in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, there was a growing need for specialists with higher technical education. As a result, the number of students at the Kyiv Polytechnic Institute grew rapidly: while 360 students were enrolled in the first year when the institute opened, by 1905 there were already more than 1,600 students. Graduates of the institution were able to replace foreign specialists in key industries, demonstrating the competitiveness of national technical education [3].

After the closure of the Main Pedagogical Institute in 1859, the function

of training teachers for secondary and specialized educational institutions was transferred to universities. Between 1859 and 1900, they trained about 58,000 specialists, including 23,500 graduates of law faculties. Legal education opened the way to public service, so the majority of students were children of nobles and officials. At the same time, the critical need for teaching staff led to university education focusing on training teachers for secondary and higher education [6].

Graduates of the painting, sculpture, and architecture departments received the titles of “artist” and “artist-architect,” which entitled them to work professionally in the arts and teaching. The number of students gradually increased: from 290 in the 1900/01 academic year to 387 in 1917, with an increase in the number of women among the students [4].

By 1914, there were 10 universities in Russia with 37,500 students; in 1916, there were 11, and about 12,000 people were enrolled each year [6].

In the 1920s and 1930s, the reform of higher education affected not only the structure of universities, but also changed academic programs, teaching methods, and forms of knowledge testing. At the end of 1935, the university system experienced a revival: restrictions based on social origin were removed, certain academic traditions were restored, and the system began to function more stable. At the same time, excessive centralization and standardization made the education process less flexible, made it harder to introduce new ideas, and held back teaching innovation [2].

After World War II, the Soviet Union had a severe shortage of highly qualified specialists for the development of radiophysics and the creation of a radio engineering industry. On the initiative of Axel Ivanovich Berg, chairman of the Committee on Radar under the Government of the USSR, a radio physics department was opened at Kharkiv University in 1952. The decision to establish the faculty was based on the scientific potential of Kharkiv, where research in the field of radio electronics was actively developing in the early 1950s. During the same period, the Department of Ultra-High Frequency Physics was established, one of the first specialized departments of the faculty. Over more than six decades of activity, the faculty has trained about six thousand specialists, of whom more than 600 have completed their master’s theses and more than 100 have completed their doctorates [13].

In the 1960s–1980s, Kharkiv became one of the leading scientific and educational centers of the Soviet Union. During this period, new educational and research institutions actively developed in the city, contributing to the formation of a powerful intellectual environment. The staff of leading higher education institutions, in particular Kharkiv State University, the Polytechnic Institute, the Law Institute, the Institute of Radio Electronics, and others, made a significant contribution to the training of highly qualified specialists and the development of science [2].

Students in the 1990s differed significantly from their Soviet counterparts focusing on practical results and the needs of the labor market. Many pursued education primarily to obtain a diploma, while employment depended not only on educational level, but also on the economic situation and market demands. Only a few universities were able to actively support the graduate employment [12].

In 1998, scholarships were established to support scientists, but most young scientists were leaving the country. In 1999, the Ministry of Education reduced the state order for training specialists in fields where the expected results had not been achieved [12].

In Ukraine, there is a growing correlation between education level and income, but there are significant problems with professional qualification standards. The gap between educational and professional qualification standards is explained by the lack of proper links between educational institutions and employers. Creating conditions that meet the requirements of the labor market is an important task for improving the training system and ensuring the effective selection of specialists. Solving problems in the social and labor sphere is only possible through the involvement of employers, employees, and society as a whole [8].

In conclusion, the development of the economy, science, and modernization, universities have increasingly focused on the practical needs of society. In the 20th century, the focus shifted from providing knowledge to fostering practical skills, adaptability, and readiness for change in graduates. Today, in the context of globalization, digitalization, and increased competition, the role of the university as an intermediary between education and employment has grown significantly, and this trend continues to develop toward deeper integration of educational processes with the real demands of the labor market.

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